

Less known crops of Mayurbhanj and their medicinal properties

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Abstract: The present study documents the traditional medicinal uses of lesser-known 19 cultivated crops in Mayurbhanj, Odisha, highlighting their potential therapeutic properties. The documentation of these wild and cultivated crops is crucial for preserving traditional knowledge, promoting sustainable use, and exploring novel applications in modern medicine. The findings underscore the importance of conducting further research and conservation of these valuable plant resources to support healthcare and community well-being.

Keywords: Cultivated crops, ethnobotany, sustainability, tribal dominated areas

Introduction

The world is facing significant food security challenges, especially with the global population projected to reach 9.7 billion by 2050 (Oluwole et al., 2023). Addressing sustainable food production, reducing malnutrition, and ensuring equitable access to nutritious food are urgent concerns (Fanzo et al., 2022). In this context, exploring alternative food sources and utilizing traditional knowledge can play a crucial role in tackling these issues (Kapoor et al., 2022). Wild and lesser-known crops have been identified as a valuable contributor to food security, nutrition, and sustainable agriculture (Nikalje et al., 2023). These crops often have unique nutritional and medicinal properties, making them essential resources for improving human health. Additionally, they can thrive in diverse environments, providing resilience against climate change and other environmental stresses (Cortes and Lopez, 2021). Tribal communities have long relied on these lesser-known crops and possess valuable traditional knowledge regarding their cultivation, processing, and medicinal uses (Ghosh-Jerath et al., 2021). This indigenous

knowledge has been passed down through generations, often through oral traditions (Kumar et al., 2013). Documenting and validating this knowledge not only help preserve cultural heritage but also unlocks new opportunities for sustainable development and innovation (Aradhana et al., 2022). However, the rapid erosion of traditional knowledge and the loss of biodiversity highlight the urgent need to document and conserve the uses of these lesser-known crops. By systematically recording and analyzing the traditional knowledge associated with these crops, researchers can identify potential new sources of nutrition, medicine, and sustainable livelihoods. Present study aims to contribute to these efforts by documenting the medicinal properties of cultivated crops in Mayurbhanj, Odisha, while emphasizing the importance of preserving traditional knowledge and promoting sustainable use of these invaluable resources.

Methodology

A floristic survey conducted in Mayurbhanj district, Odisha, from 2023 to 2025, identified and catalogued a range of lesser-known crops that are of significant interest for agricultural diversity and innovation (Kumar et al., 2021; Jena et al., 2025). Furthermore, the medicinal properties associated with these identified plants were systematically compiled through a comprehensive literature review employing standardized methodologies (Kumar, 2025).

Results and discussion

The study documented 19 cultivated crops in Mayurbhanj, Odisha, known for their significant medicinal properties (Table 1). These crops have traditional uses in treating various health issues, including cardiovascular disease, diabetes, respiratory problems, digestive issues, and skin conditions. The findings emphasize the importance of these crops in local healthcare systems and their potential for further research and development. The documented crops, such as *Arachis hypogaea*, *Celosia argentea*, and *Cymbopogon citratus*, among others, exhibited promising medicinal properties, including antioxidant, anti-inflammatory, and antimicrobial activities. These results highlight the value of traditional knowledge and the underscore the need for further studies to explore the pharmacological potential of these crops, ultimately contributing to the development of novel treatments and sustainable healthcare solutions.

Table 1: Less known cultivated crops of Mayurbhanj, Odisha and their medicinal properties

Cultivated crops	Medicinal uses	Source
<i>Arachis hypogaea</i> L.	Seeds and seed oil is used to reduce cardiovascular diseases.	Suchoszek-Lukaniuk et al., (2011)
<i>Basella alba</i> L.	Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory properties.	Deshmukh and Gaikwad, (2014)
<i>Brassica juncea</i> (L.) Czern. (Figure 3)	Leaves are used to boost energy, increase urine production, and help with Parkinson's disease symptoms.	Saleem et al., (2021)

<i>Cajanus cajan</i> (L.) Huth	Floral decoctions are used for bronchitis, coughs and pneumonia.	Aja et al., (2015)
<i>Celosia argentea</i> L. (Figure 6)	Seeds are widely used in folk medicine for treatment of diabetes mellitus.	Ahamed et al., (2018)
<i>Cenchrus americanus</i> (L.) Morrone	Traditionally used as a tonic and for heart disease.	Mushtaq et al., (2015)
<i>Cicer arietinum</i> L.	Used to soothe stomach burning and treat dyspepsia.	Singh and Gahlot, (2018)
<i>Cucumis melo</i> L.	Pulp or juice has been used traditionally to treat skin conditions like eczema.	Vishwakarma et al., (2017)
<i>Curcuma caesia</i> Roxb.	Rhizomes and leaf essential oil obtained from leaves have significant antioxidant activity.	Borah et al., (2021)
<i>Cymbopogon citratus</i> (DC.) Stapf (Figure 7)	Ayurvedic medicine utilizes lemongrass to ease pain related to arthritis, muscle cramps and joint discomfort.	Kiani et al., (2022)
<i>Cymbopogon flexuosus</i> (Nees ex Steud.) Will. Watson	Seed oil is effective against certain fungal infections, like ringworm.	Gao et al., 2020
<i>Eleusine coracana</i> (L.) Gaertn. (Figure 4)	Helps to regulate blood sugar levels and activates insulin production.	Agrawal et al., (2023)
<i>Helianthus annuus</i> L. (Figure 1)	Tea made from leaves has astringent, diuretic and expectorant properties.	Al-Snafi, (2018)
<i>Hibiscus sabdariffa</i> L. (Figure 2)	Traditionally used for improving digestion and relieving constipation.	Montalvo-González et al., (2022)
<i>Leucas aspera</i> (Willd.) Link (Figure 5)	Roots have analgesic activity. Whole plant has potential anthelmintic properties.	Das et al., (2012)
<i>Macrotyloma uniflorum</i> (Lam.) Verdc.	Traditionally seeds are used to treat kidney stones.	Patel and Acharya, (2020)
<i>Paspalum scrobiculatum</i> L.	Plant has anti-hyperlipidaemic activity, that helps to lower cholesterol levels.	Narra et al., (2013)

<i>Sorghum bicolor</i> (L.) Moench	It is useful in treatment of anaemia, and infectious diseases.	Senou et al., (2016)
<i>Vigna radiata</i> (L.) R. Wilczek	Used in traditional medicine for conditions like paralysis, rheumatism and liver ailments.	Ganesan and Xu, (2018)

Figure 1: Flowers of *Helianthus annuus*

Figure 2: Flowers of *Hibiscus sabdariffa*

Figure 3: Flowers of *Brassica juncea*

Figure 4: Cultivation of *Eleusine corcana*

Figure 5: Flowers of *Leucas aspera*

Figure 6: Flowers of *Celosia argentea*

Figure 7: Cultivation of *Cymbopogon flexuosus*

Conclusion

The present study emphasizes the significance of documenting and preserving traditional knowledge associated with cultivated crops in Mayurbhanj, Odisha. The findings highlight the potential of these crops in addressing various health issues, underscoring their significance in local healthcare systems. The preservation and promotion of indigenous crops, especially lesser-known medicinally important plants, has multiple benefits. These crops contribute significantly to the biodiversity conservation and helps in maintaining the ecological balance by sustaining local ecosystems. By conserving and promoting these valuable resources, we can unlock new opportunities for sustainable development, innovation, and improved healthcare outcomes. Additionally, these species symbolize the heritage of the local regions. Local communities depend on them not just for sustenance but also as a part of their identity and traditions. By preserving and conserving these lesser-known plant species we can honour the agricultural wisdom that has been passed down through generations. Embracing these indigenous crops will not only improve the healthcare systems but will also safeguard our natural resources and foster the economic growth within rural communities. Revitalizing the interest in traditionally cultivated lesser-known medicinal species can lead to healthier lifestyles and enrich cultural narratives across various geographical regions.

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